

Comparison of the Efficacy and Safety of Silodosin and Tamsulosin in Treatment of Benign Prostatic Hypertrophy

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Objective:** To compare the efficacy and safety of Silodosin and Tamsulosin in treatment of Benign Prostatic Hypertrophy.**Methods:** Our study is an observational and comparative study of 120 patients. The patients were divided into two groups of 60 patients each – Silodosin Group and Tamsulosin Group. During the study 11 patient from the Silodosin group and 12 patients from the Tamsulosin group dropped out and 49 & 48 patients respectively from the groups were available till the end of the study.**Results:** The mean age, mean weight and duration of symptoms in both the groups was comparable and statistically not significant. The rate of improvement in the QLS was similar in both the groups, with gradual improvement towards the end of the study period, indicating that the onset of improvement in the QLS corresponds to the decrease in IPSS. There was insignificant difference in Qmax from baseline, the mean change was 0.12 mL/s (1.07%) & 0.25 mL/s (2.11%) for Silodosin and Tamsulosin group respectively.

There were no significant changes in prostate volume and postvoid residual volumes in either group. Significant improvement was observed in different parameters in both the groups by the end of the study period. Six of the seven parameters were significantly improved. Regarding adverse events in our study, both treatments were well-accepted as assessed by various parameters. The events encountered were both mild in nature and transient. The most specific adverse reaction was retrograde ejaculation found in 3 patients in Silodosin group (and none in Tamsulosin group).

Conclusion: Silodosin is comparable to Tamsulosin in the treatment of symptomatic BPH in Indian men. Both offer symptom relief without affecting prostate size in the short-term. Retrograde ejaculation was encountered only with Silodosin. This may influence the choice of drug – Tamsulosin for comparatively younger sexually active men. Further clinical studies, of longer duration, are needed to confirm whether this comparability in the treatment of BPH is sustained in the long term.**Keywords:** Silodosin, Tamsulosin, Benign Prostatic Hypertrophy, Lower Urinary Symptoms (LUTS), Bladder Outlet Obstruction (BOO), Quality of Life (QOL).This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is a nonmalignant enlargement of the prostate caused by cellular hyperplasia of both glandular and stromal element [1]. As the prostate increase in size, it may occlude the lumen of the prostatic urethra, obstructing urine flow. However studies have shown that prostate size and urinary flow rate usually do not correlate with the severity of lower urinary symptoms (LUTS), which may vary from subject to subject [2]. In clinical practice, patients are treated for LUTS suggestive of bladder outlet obstruction (BOO) due to BPH often called “LUTS/BPH”.

Even if voiding symptoms are most prevalent in case of LUTS/ BPH patient usually perceive the storage symptoms as the most bothersome group of

symptoms.[3] The objective of therapy for such patient is to improve LUTS/BPH and hence quality of life (QOL). In addition treatment is aimed at preventing complication such as Acute Urinary Retention or Upper Urinary Tract Dilatation consequent to BOO. Existing medical therapy include α -blockers, which are currently preferred first line treatment for all men with moderate to severe LUTS/BPH [4] and 5 α -reductase inhibitors (5-ARI). α -blockers can be used regardless of prostate size because they act on the dynamic/ neutrally mediated contraction of the muscular stroma that is increased in BPH; 5-ARIs act by shrinking the stromal components of the gland. Both components are thought to contribute to

the symptoms and impairment of out flow in patient with LUTS/BPH.[5]

Nonselective α 1-adrenoceptor blockers increase urinary flow rate and improve symptoms in men with symptomatic BPH; however they may be associated with side effects related to peripheral vasodilation such as postural hypotension, dizziness and headache[6-8]. Conversely drugs with a high affinity for α 1a-adrenoreceptor may be more prostate specific and may maintain the therapeutic response in the treatment of symptomatic BPH with less effect on blood pressure and fewer cardiovascular side effects.

Silodosin is a new agent with high selectivity for α 1a receptor which predominate in the male bladder outflow tract relative to α 1b receptor. It has been demonstrated in vitro that silodosin α 1a to α 1b.binding ratio is extremely high, suggesting the potential to markedly reduce dynamic neurally mediated smooth muscle relaxation in the lower urinary tract while minimizing undesirable effects on blood pressure regulation[11]. In this context the evaluation of the Uroselectivity of Silodosin versus Tamsulosin in vivo has shown good uroselectivity in rats and dogs[12,13] The study compared Silodosin with the effective and widely used drug Tamsulosin.[14]

Materials and Methods

Study Design: This is observational and comparative study

Study Site: This study was conducted in the Department of Pharmacology in collaboration with Department of Urology in J K Hospital and L N Medical College. All cases of BPH treated in hospital OPD.

Sample Size: Minimum 50 for each group.

Duration of Study: 12 months.

Ethical Consideration: The Study was conducted after obtaining permission from the Ethics Committee and Department of Urology. All the data collected as a part of this study was kept strictly confidential and used for the purpose of this study only. Steps taken by us to maintain confidentiality were:

1. Identification of patients by the case paper number only and not by name.
2. Case records to be assessed by the principle investigator, co- investigator and Urologist only.
3. Patient details not to be divulged to any party.

Sample Size: Minimum 50 for each group.

Selection Criteria: Patient case papers satisfying following inclusion and exclusion criteria will be thoroughly examined and followed.

Inclusion Criteria

- a. Age > 50 Year
- b. Gender - Male
- c. with symptoms of moderate to severe BPH (IPSS >7)
- d. Race - Indian

Exclusion Criteria

PATIENT WITH

- a. Prostate cancer
- b. Urethral Stricture
- c. Apparent neurogenic bladder
- d. Those on medication that might effect voiding such as anticholinergic and antiandrogen Drugs
- e. Diabetes mellitus, spinal trauma.

Study Procedure: Patients diagnosed with Benign prostatic hypertrophy were enrolled in the study as per inclusion and exclusion criteria. Patients were explained in detail about the study i.e. purpose of the study, procedure of the study, possible benefit of this study and about their data confidentiality. Above information was explained in participant information sheet (PIS). The data was collected from patient's prescribed case paper after obtaining written informed consent. Collected data was noted on case record form (CRF).

Material/ Instruments Used for the Study: Sphygmomanometer, Stethoscope, Uroflowmeter, drug silodosin 8mg tamsulosin 0.4mg.

Data Collection: Data was obtained from the prescribed case paper of patients after taking written informed consent and was recorded in Case Record Form (CRF). The following parameters were noted.

Observations and Results

Our study is an observational and comparative study of 120 patients to compare the efficacy and safety of Silodosin and Tamsulosin in treatment of Benign Prostatic Hypertrophy. The patients were divided into two groups of 60 patients each – Silodosin Group and Tamsulosin Group. During the study 11 patient from the Silodosin group and 12 patients from the Tamsulosin group dropped out and 49 & 48 patients respectively from the groups were available till the end of the study.

Distribution of Patients According to Age: Silodosin Group had 13 patients (26.5%) in the age group of 51-60 years, 17 patients (34.7%) in the age group of 61-70 years and 19 (38.8%) patients in greater than 70 years of age group. The mean age was 65.6 ± 7.86 . Tamsulosin Group had 12 patients (25%) in the age group of 51-60 years, 19 patients (39.6%) in the age group of 61-70 years and 17 (35.4%) patients in greater than 70 years of age group. The mean age was 65.13 ± 8.13 . The age of

the patients was comparable between the two groups and statistically not significant (p=0.821).

Table 1: Distribution of patients according to age

Age (in yrs)	Silodosin Group		Tamsulosin Group	
	F	%	F	%
51-60	13	26.5%	12	25%
61-70	17	34.7%	19	39.6%
>70	19	38.8%	17	35.4%
Total	49	100%	48	100%
Mean ± SD	65.6±7.86		65.13±8.13	

IPSS Changes in the study groups

There was significant decline in IPSS scores by the end of the study period in both the groups (p=0.001).

There was significant difference when any of the follow-up visits was compared with the corresponding baseline (p=0.001). However there was insignificant difference between the groups.

Table 2: IPSS Changes in the study groups

	Baseline	21 Days	3 months	6 months	12 months	18 months
Silodosin Group	18.57 ± 1.57	14.89 ± 2.84	13.62 ± 2.63	12.62 ± 2.27	9.86 ± 0.99	6.27 ± 1.26
Within Group 'P'		0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001
Tamsulosin Group	18.87 ± 2.26	15.12 ± 1.45	14.16 ± 1.72	13.42 ± 1.99	10.32 ± 1.30	6.77 ± 1.65
Within Group 'P'		0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001
Between group P	0.552	0.618	0.235	0.152	0.128	0.192

Quality of Life Score (QLS) in the study groups

There was significant increase in QLS by the end of the study period in both the groups (p=0.001). There

was significant difference when any of the follow-up visits was compared with the corresponding baseline (p=0.001). However there was insignificant difference.

Table 3: QLS Values in the study groups

	Baseline	21 Days	3 months	6 months	12 months	18 months
Silodosin Group	4.72 ± 0.43	2.74± 0.21	2.51± 0.52	1.96 ± 0.56	1.43 ± 0.26	1.18 ± 0.14
Within Group 'P'		0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001
Tamsulosin Group	4.52 ± 0.39	2.86± 0.41	2.41± 0.35	2.17 ± 0.22	1.52 ± 0.34	1.23 ± 0.19
Within Group 'P'		0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001
Between group P	0.064	0.071	0.235	0.061	0.254	0.251

Peak Flow Rate (Qmax) in the study groups

There was no significant difference from baseline at the end of the study period in both the groups. At the end of the study the mean change was 0.12 mL/s

(1.07%) & 0.25 mL/s (2.11%) for Silodosin and Tamsulosin group respectively but the change was not significant enough. These parameters did not change significantly between the groups also.

Table 4: Peak Flow Rate (Qmax) in the study groups

	Baseline	21 Days	3 months	6 months	12 months	18 months
Silodosin Group	11.24 ± 0.78	11.48± 0.51	11.44± 0.32	11.41± 0.36	11.39± 0.25	11.36 ± 0.22
Within Group ‘P’		0.077	0.103	0.173	0.207	0.307
Tamsulosin Group	11.80 ± 0.97	12.18± 0.98	12.15± 0.96	12.13± 0.93	12.08± 0.91	12.05 ± 0.89
Within Group ‘P’		0.067	0.078	0.10	0.148	0.196
Between group P	0.173	0.071	0.235	0.305	0.187	0.157

USG findings of Prostrate Parameters in the study groups There were no significant changes in prostate volume and postvoid residual volumes in either group.

Table 5: USG findings of Prostrate Parameters in the study groups

USG findings of Prostrate Parameters		Baseline	End of Study Period	Within Group P
Prostrate Volume (ml)	Silodosin Group	42.5 ± 18.75	38.4 ± 19.35	0.408
	Tamsulosin Group	35.6 ± 9.56	34.7 ± 15.52	0.787
	Between group P	0.077	0.417	
Postvoid Residual Volume (ml)	Silodosin Group	49.2 ± 50.38	79.6 ± 98.64	0.138
	Tamsulosin Group	58.9 ± 65.62	47.4 ± 71.74	0.519
	Between group P	0.523	0.153	

Pre and Post Treatment Parameters in the study groups Significant improvement was observed in different parameters in both the groups by the end of the study period. Six of the seven parameters were

significantly improved (Incomplete Emptying, Frequency, Intermittency, Urgency, Weak Stream, Straining). There was less improvement in nocturia compared to other parameters.

Table 6: Pre and Post Treatment Parameters in the study groups

Pre and Post Treatment Parameters		Baseline	End of Study Period	Within Group P
Incomplete Emptying	Silodosin Group	1.9 ± 0.55	1.1 ± 0.03	0.0001
	Tamsulosin Group	1.8 ± 0.27	1.1 ± 0.05	0.0001
	Between group P	0.375	1.00	
Frequency	Silodosin Group	2.5 ± 0.31	1.9 ± 0.48	0.0001
	Tamsulosin Group	2.4 ± 0.30	1.7 ± 0.37	0.0001
	Between group P	0.209	0.075	
Intermittency	Silodosin Group	2.7 ± 0.45	1.8 ± 0.38	0.0001
	Tamsulosin Group	2.4 ± 0.45	1.7 ± 0.15	0.0001
	Between group P	0.012	0.185	
Urgency	Silodosin Group	1.4 ± 1.2	0.7 ± 0.5	0.0046
	Tamsulosin Group	2.0 ± 1.6	0.9 ± 1.1	0.003
	Between group P	0.105	0.368	
Weak Stream	Silodosin Group	3.6 ± 1.4	2.6 ± 1.2	0.0043
	Tamsulosin Group	3.1 ± 1.5	1.9 ± 1.6	0.004
	Between group P	0.187	0.060	
Straining	Silodosin Group	2.6 ± 1.4	1.4 ± 1.1	0.0005
	Tamsulosin Group	1.6 ± 1.3	0.9 ± 1.0	0.022
	Between group P	0.006	0.070	
Nocturia	Silodosin Group	2.3 ± 1.0	1.9 ± 0.8	0.092
	Tamsulosin Group	2.4 ± 1.1	1.8 ± 1.5	0.082
	Between group P	0.713	0.748	

Adverse Events in the study groups Regarding tolerability in our study, both treatments were well-accepted as assessed by clinical and laboratory parameters. The events encountered were both mild

in nature and transient. The most specific adverse reaction was retrograde ejaculation found in 3 patients in Silodosin group (and none in Tamsulosin group).

Table 7: Adverse Events in the study groups

Adverse Events	Silodosin Group	Tamsulosin Group
Ejaculation Disorder	3	0
Constipation	1	1
Dry Mouth	2	0
Skin Rash	1	0

Results

- The mean age of the patients was comparable between the two groups with mean age in Silodosin Group being 65.6 ± 7.86 and that in Tamsulosin Group being 65.13 ± 8.13 . The difference was statistically not significant ($p=0.821$).
- The mean weight and duration of symptoms in both the groups was comparable and statistically not significant ($p=0.223$ & $p=0.087$ respectively).
- There was significant decline in IPSS scores by the end of the study period in both the groups ($p=0.001$). There was (-12.3; 66.2%) and (-12.1; 64.1%) decline in IPSS score in Silodosin and Tamsulosin Group respectively.
- There was significant increase in QLS by end of the study period. The rate of improvement in the QLS was similar in both the groups, with gradual improvement towards the end of the study period, indicating that the onset of improvement in the QLS corresponds to the decrease in IPSS.
- In our study there was insignificant difference in Qmax from baseline at the end of the study period in both the groups. At the end of the study the mean change was 0.12 mL/s (1.07%) & 0.25 mL/s (2.11%) for Silodosin and Tamsulosin group respectively.
- There were no significant changes in prostate volume and postvoid residual volumes in either group.
- Significant improvement was observed in different parameters in both the groups by the end of the study period. Six of the seven parameters were significantly improved (Incomplete Emptying, Frequency, Intermittency, Urgency, Weak Stream, Straining)
- Regarding adverse events in our study, both treatments were well-accepted as assessed by various parameters. The events encountered were both mild in nature and transient. The most specific adverse reaction was retrograde ejaculation found in 3 patients in Silodosin group (and none in Tamsulosin group).

Statistical Analysis: The collected data was summarized by using frequency, percentage, mean & S.D. To compare the qualitative outcome measures Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test was used. To compare the quantitative outcome measures independent t test was used. If data was not following normal distribution, Mann Whitney U test was used. SPSS version 22 software was used to analyse the collected data. p value of <0.05 was statistically significant.

Discussion

Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is a nonmalignant enlargement of the prostate caused by cellular hyperplasia of both glandular and stromal element[1]. According to the European Association of Urology 2011 guidelines[2] α -blockers are

currently the preferred first-line therapy for all men with moderate or severe LUTS/BPH and 5 α -reductase inhibitors (5-ARI). α -blockers can be used regardless of prostate size because they act on the dynamic/neutral mediated contraction of the muscular stroma that is increased in BPH; 5-ARIs act by shrinking the stromal components of the gland. Both components are thought to contribute to the symptoms and impairment of out flow in patient with LUTS/BPH.

Our study is an observational and comparative study of 120 patients to compare the efficacy and safety of Silodosin and Tamsulosin in treatment of Benign Prostatic Hypertrophy. The patients were divided into two groups of 30 patients each – Silodosin Group and Tamsulosin Group. During the study 11 patient from the Silodosin group and 12 patients from the Tamsulosin group dropped out and 49 & 48 patients respectively from the groups were available till the end of the study.

The mean age of the patients was comparable between the two groups with mean age in Silodosin Group being 65.6 ± 7.86 and that in Tamsulosin Group being 65.13 ± 8.13 . The difference was statistically not significant ($p=0.821$). The mean weight and duration of symptoms in both the groups was comparable and statistically not significant ($p=0.223$ & $p=0.087$ respectively). Thus with respect to demographic variables both the groups were comparable. The importance of the variation being non-significant for age, weight and duration of symptom is that a random distribution of patients was confirmed to and there were no confounding factors which would later interfere with the assessment.

In the present study, there was significant decline in IPSS scores by the end of the study period in both the groups ($p=0.001$). There was (-12.3; 66.2%) and (-12.1; 64.1%) decline in IPSS score in Silodosin and Tamsulosin Group respectively. This is in concordant to the studies of Chapple et al.[3], Yu et. al.[4], Kawabe et. al.[5] and Marks et. al.[6]. In a multi-centric RCT conducted by Chapple et al.[3] it was found that the change from baseline in the IPSS total score with both Silodosin and Tamsulosin was significantly superior to that with placebo: Difference between placebo and active drug was -2.3 (95% confidence interval [CI], -3.2 to -1.4) with Silodosin and -2.0 (95% CI, -2.9 to -1.1) with Tamsulosin. Responder rates according to total IPSS were significantly higher with Silodosin (66.8%) and Tamsulosin (65.4%) than with placebo (50.8%). Chapple et al.[3] concluded that the overall efficacy of Silodosin is not inferior to Tamsulosin.

Another non-inferiority trial conducted by Yu et. al.[4] found that, of the 170 (81.3%) patients who completed the study, 86.2% in the Silodosin group versus 81.9% in the Tamsulosin group achieved a

$\geq 25\%$ decrease in IPSS ($P = 0.53$). The mean difference (Silodosin minus Tamsulosin) in IPSS change from baseline was -0.60 (95% CI -2.15 to -0.95), showed the non-inferiority of Silodosin 4mg twice daily to Tamsulosin 0.2mg once daily in patients with symptomatic BPH. The first double-blind, placebo-controlled, RCT comparing Tamsulosin and Silodosin was reported in 2006 by Kawabe et. al.[5]. Patients received Silodosin 4 mg twice daily, Tamsulosin 0.2 mg once daily, or a placebo for 12-week. The changes in the total IPSS from the baseline in the Silodosin, Tamsulosin, and placebo groups were -8.3 , -6.8 and -5.3 respectively. Kawabe et. al.[5] concluded that the Silodosin was better than a placebo and not inferior to Tamsulosin. Marks et. al.[6] from a pooled analysis of two RCTs in United States reported that symptom relief was rapid and differences (Silodosin versus Placebo) in IPSS score and sub scores increased by week 12.

The rate of improvement in the QLS was similar in both the groups, with gradual improvement towards the end of the study period, indicating that the onset of improvement in the QLS corresponds to the decrease in IPSS. The study of Rossi M. et. al.[7] has also observed a similar pattern of parallel improvement in the IPSS and QLS. In the study of Rossi M. et. al.[7], they reviewed the clinical efficacy of Silodosin for the treatment of LUTS/BPH using five clinical studies conducted in Japan and the US. The primary endpoint of the trial was the total IPSS change from baseline, and secondary endpoints were change in Qmax, QoL score, and IPSS voiding and storage scores. For QoL score, the change from baseline was -1.7 (1.4), -1.4 (1.3), and -1.1 (1.2) in the Silodosin, Tamsulosin, and placebo groups, respectively. Therefore, Silodosin was significantly better than placebo in terms of IPSS and QoL scores ($P < 0.001$ and $P = 0.002$ respectively). As compared with Tamsulosin, Silodosin showed no significant difference concerning IPSS and QoL scores.

In our study there was insignificant difference in Qmax from baseline at the end of the study period in both the groups. At the end of the study the mean change was 0.12 mL/s (1.07%) & 0.25 mL/s (2.11%) for Silodosin and Tamsulosin group respectively but the change was not significant enough. These parameters did not change significantly between the groups also. Also the improvement in Qmax was maximum with Tamsulosin and lesser improvement with Silodosin. This may be probably because of various other factors which may influence voiding such as fullness of bladder, intra-abdominal pressure generated during voiding and voiding conditions. Our findings are in conformity with those in the studies of Chapple et al.[3] Chapple et al.[3] reported that an increase in Qmax was observed in all groups—the adjusted mean change

from baseline to end was 3.77 mL/s for Silodosin, 3.53 mL/s for Tamsulosin, and 2.93 mL/s for placebo, but the changes for Silodosin and Tamsulosin were not statistically significant versus placebo because of a particularly high placebo response. At end-point, the percentage of responders by Qmax was 46.6%, 46.5%, and 40.5% in the Silodosin, Tamsulosin, and placebo treatment groups, respectively. These differences in proportions were also not statistically significant.

There were no significant changes in prostate volume and postvoid residual volumes in either group and this is like the findings of Yu et al.[4]. Yu et al⁴ have also reported that the changes in mean Qmax from baseline were comparable between Tamsulosin and Silodosin, and both were not statistically different from respective baseline. There was no significant reduction in prostate volume after 12-week of therapy in either group. Significant improvement was observed in different parameters in both the groups by the end of the study period. Six of the seven parameters were significantly improved (Incomplete Emptying, Frequency, Intermittency, Urgency, Weak Stream, Straining). This is in concordance to the study of Takeshita H et. al.[8]. Takeshita H et. al.[8] conducted an eight week, open-label, randomized crossover study between 2011 and 2014 at four community-based hospitals in Japan. Thirty-four participants were randomly divided into two groups. Significant improvement in total IPSS was observed in the initial treatment period in both the groups. Also six of the seven IPSS items were significantly improved. There was less improvement in nocturia compared to other parameters. Our observations were consistent with study of Rossi M. et. al.[7]. Subjective improvement in nocturia was noted specifically with Silodosin in the study of Takeshita H et. al.[8] which was a randomized cross-over comparison of half-dose Silodosin with Tamsulosin.

Regarding adverse events in our study, both treatments were well-accepted as assessed by various parameters. The events encountered were both mild in nature and transient. The most specific adverse reaction was retrograde ejaculation found in 3 patients in Silodosin group (and none in Tamsulosin group). The ejaculatory dysfunction is usually not related to BPH, but may occur due to various other factors such as aging, comorbid conditions such as diabetes, autonomic dysfunction, and it is a known side effect of α -blockers due to impaired contraction of vas deferens[7]. The overall incidence of the ejaculatory dysfunction was more common in Silodosin group (10%). This is consistent with the observations in study of Rossi M. et. al.[7] which have reported up to 28% with Silodosin. In fact, worsening of sexual function scores was observed with Silodosin alone in one of the studies but not with Tamsulosin at the end of 12

weeks treatment[9]. Abnormal ejaculation is the most reported adverse event with Silodosin and has been reported as the main reason behind its discontinuation in the study of Keating GM[10]. A population-based cohort study by Welk B et. al.[11] on men aged ≥ 66 years showed that α -blockers significantly increase the risk of falling, sustaining a fracture and trauma when compared with the unexposed cohort. All the adverse events with the study medications were of Level 1 severity, not warranting discontinuation or substitution indicating a good tolerability in the dose employed. The patient compliance for the study medications was good.

Some of the limitations of the study were small sample size, short duration of follow-up and the study involving a single centre. Further, elaborate multi-centric studies involving a larger number of subjects from different geographical regions, with different comorbid conditions and risk factors, concomitant medications, and a longer duration of therapy, may be undertaken to generate more data regarding the relative efficacy and tolerability of these medications and also to detect very rare or unusual adverse effects.

Conclusion

Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is a nonmalignant enlargement of the prostate caused by cellular hyperplasia of both glandular and stromal element. In clinical practice, patients are treated for LUTS suggestive of bladder outlet obstruction (BOO) due to BPH often called "LUTS/BPH". Even if voiding symptoms are most prevalent in case of LUTS/ BPH patient usually perceive the storage symptoms as the most bothersome group of symptoms. The objective of therapy for such patient is to improve LUTS/BPH and hence quality of life (QOL). In addition treatment is aimed at preventing complication such as Acute Urinary Retention or Upper Urinary Tract Dilatation consequent to BOO. Existing medical therapy include α -blockers, which are currently preferred first line treatment for all men with moderate to severe LUTS/BPH and 5 α -reductase inhibitors (5-ARI).

It can be said that Silodosin is comparable to Tamsulosin in the treatment of symptomatic BPH in Indian men. Both offer symptom relief without affecting prostate size in the short-term. Retrograde ejaculation was encountered only with Silodosin. This may influence the choice of drug – Tamsulosin for comparatively younger sexually active men. Further clinical studies, of longer duration, are needed to confirm whether this comparability in the treatment of BPH is sustained in the long term.

Declarations:

Funding: None **Conflicts of interest/Competing interests:** None **Availability of data and material:** Department of Pharmacology in collaboration with

Department of Urology in J K Hospital and L N Medical College **Code availability:** Not applicable **Consent to participate:** Consent taken **Ethical Consideration:** There are no ethical conflicts related to this study. **Consent for publication:** Consent taken

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